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Modern Psychotherapy as a Multidimensional Multilevel Evolutionary Process

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Abstract

Modern evidence-based psychotherapy can be understood by consideration of six key concepts from evolution science that have an impact on behavioral science: variation, selection, retention, dimensions, levels, and context. Human behavior problems are most likely to emerge when repertoires are narrow or rigid, are under inappropriate selection criteria targeted at the wrong level or dimension, and without retention of successful variants that are fitted to context. Modern effective psychotherapies represent the inverse process of creating broad and flexible repertoires, selected by personal values, and fitted to particular contexts at the appropriate level and in the right dimension. Psychotherapy can thus be considered an applied evolution science.

Modern Psychotherapy as a Multidimensional Multilevel Evolutionary Process

Behavior therapy emerged from the extension of basic behavioral principles identified in the animal laboratory into complex human behavior [1]. That bottom up approach faltered with the arrival of cognitive behavior therapy, however, because no basic theory of cognition was available that proved adequate to broadly focused clinical work and as such clinical theories of cognition were pursued instead [2].

The “contextual behavioral science” (CBS) wing of modern behavioral and cognitive therapy is revisiting that strategic choice. CBS is a term for a functional, contextual vision of behavior analysis that embraces a central role for human cognition approached in a functional and contextual way [3]. CBS researchers and theorists have developed Relational Frame Theory (RFT) as a working account of the cognitive domain [4] and have applied RFT and behavioral principles to clinical situations [e.g., 5,6,7].

CBS has also revisited Skinner’s idea that behavioral principles need to be situated more generally as part of the science of selection by consequences, an approach that in essence defines behavioral psychology as a wing of evolution science [8]. In Skinner’s day that was a difficult bridge to build because of the gene centrism of evolutionists at the time, but today’s modern multi-dimensional and multi-level evolution science affords a set of concepts and findings that allow this alliance to be far more substantive (e.g., see [9]). The present short paper provides an overview in thumbnail form of how evidence-based psychotherapy (focusing in particular on third wave behavior therapy) can be usefully nested within modern evolution science.

Multi-Dimensional Evolution

We consider an evolutionary account to be any that examines the function, mechanisms, development, and history of a phenomenon [10] in terms of variation, selection, and retention

within and across lifetimes [11]. Most behavioral and life scientists are used to thinking of genetics in such a way, but not behavior or cognition. Two broad changes in evolution science are making that link more possible. The first is multi-dimensionality. In the modern era we know that evolution involves much more than genes. Epigenetic processes such as DNA methylation or histone modification are heritable processes that regulate gene expression [12] and that are known to be involved in the production of physical, behavioral, and cognitive phenotypes.

Behavior regulated by contingency learning has long been argued by behavior analysts to be an evolutionary process within the lifetime of the individual– but it is clear now that behavior and learning continue to a degree across lifetimes due to cultural practices, social learning processes, niche selection, and niche construction [12] and due to the impact of learning on epigenetic processes. Indeed, recent evidence suggests that some forms of operant and classical conditioning directly impact progeny as a result of interactions between these evolutionary dimensions (e.g., [13]). Operant learning also puts organisms into regular contact with specific aspects of the environment to which they may then become more adapted. For example, the reinforcing effectiveness of crustaceans ensure that flamingoes hunt regularly for food in river mud and that regular contact in turn allows the beaks of flamingoes to evolve based on the natural selection of beak variations that make hunting crustaceans more successful. Because of such processes, contingency learning has been proposed as the single most important factor contributing to the “Cambrian Explosion” – the proliferation of species seen 540 Mya –when contingency learning first appeared [14]. All of these facts point to the key role of behavior and learning in genetic evolution and assimilation.

Human language, the use of symbols to represent events and to alter their functions, arguably constitutes an inheritance system in its own right with its own recent forms of selection

(e.g., retelling; retweeting) and retention (e.g., books; disk drives). CBS theorists have argued that symbolic behavior was likely initially selected by its ability to extend human cooperation due to the mutual entailment of symbol → object relations through social perspective taking [15]. As the ability to derive relations among events increased, people became sensitive to the internal coherence of networks of symbols and the relations among them and with external events that were established via human language [16] thus providing a tool for human problem solving [4]. The use of symbols in this way also readily impacted cultural practices, social learning, niche selection, niche construction, and epigenetics [12].

Multi-Level Selection

Multi-level selection refers to the fact that selection can operate simultaneously at the level of individual units (e.g., cells; individual organisms; specific actions) and collections of such unit (e.g., multicellular organisms, groups, repertoires) [17]. Given a particular environmental context, the interests of an individual may become best served by means of cooperation in a group, which can be successfully selected provided individual selfishness is suppressed [18]. Major evolutionary transitions tend to consist of exactly such sets of conditions. Examples are provided by the development of eukaryotic cells, multicellular organisms, and eusocial species.

Evolutionary Principles

At least six key concepts from evolution science are key when considering its implications for behavioral science. Five have been mentioned: variation, selection, retention, dimensions, and levels. The sixth is context, which determines the success of the first five, and which is especially central when evolution is used to guide purposive change.

Psychotherapy and Behavior Change as an Evolutionary Process

We will very briefly consider each of these six concepts as they apply to psychotherapy and behavior change, emphasizing examples from modern contextual forms of cognitive behavior therapy. It is our argument that all intransient human problems involve deficits in one or more of these six areas and that all successful forms of psychotherapy and behavior change modify them, but that this is especially obvious in third wave interventions.

Variation

Narrow and rigid repertoires cannot evolve as readily as broad and flexible repertoires. It is worth noting that clients often describe themselves as “stuck” or “in a rut.” Perhaps the single most powerful enemy of healthy behavioral variation is aversive control that leads to patterns of avoidance. Avoidance reduces contact with events that might otherwise shape behavior, thus undermining unnecessary avoidance should be a key focus of psychotherapy in order to create healthy behavioral variation.

It appears to have such a focus. For example, exposure is a key component of most forms of evidence-based psychotherapy for this reason. We now know that exposure does not work by a reduction of emotional responses per se – rather it works by changing the person’s relationship with targets of avoidance [19]. From an evolution science point of view exposure provides organized contact with previously repertoire narrowing events in a context designed to produce broader and more flexible repertoires in their presence [5]. Operant extinction itself appears to work this way, leading to the deployment of previously learned repertoires [20,21] and ultimately to novel behaviors.

A second major process leading to restricted behavioral variation is excessive rule-governance [22,23]. Verbal rules can dominate over direct experience in the regulation of behavior (see [24] for a book length review). In a broad sense verbal relations are an enormous

source of variation, allowing humans to plan, and to respond to remote or delayed consequences, but in clinical situations they have become restrictive by blocking out the impact of more direct contingencies. A primary way verbal rules impact sensitivity to direct contingencies is that verbal symbols take on some of the stimulus properties of the events they are related to [4,25] and may become both targets and means of avoidance. For example, the recounting of a traumatic memory may evoke the same physiological arousal and escape and avoidance responses as the event itself. Attempts to deliberately change or reduce the form or frequency of private experiences such as bodily sensations, emotions, thoughts, or urges, or to avoid the contexts which evoke them, are referred to as experiential avoidance [26]. Experiential avoidance is a rule-based form of avoidance that greatly amplifies the ability of events to create narrow and rigid repertoires because verbal relations can focus on the presence of historically produced private events (e.g., memories, emotions, thoughts) and not merely situational ones. Attempts to avoid or suppress private events have the paradoxical effect of making them more frequent and therefore more central in the individual's life [27,29].

Mindfulness, acceptance, and defusion skills are central to third wave interventions (for a recent review see [29]). These methods are designed to undermine experiential avoidance, to reduce the automatic impact of verbal rules, and to increase attentional flexibility. To the extent that these processes change, they mediate broader and more flexible repertoires [30], precisely as would be expected from an evolutionary perspective.

Consider the case of a client who suffers from panic attacks and has the thought "I can't go to the mall, I'd be overwhelmed and lose control." Taken literally, this rule relates going to the mall to a high likelihood of harm; and in order to go to the mall, the person must be going to the mall thus requires being convinced otherwise. Acceptance, mindfulness, and defusion skills

help the person see that thought merely as a thought which may or may not be useful and which has no set relationship to actually going to the mall. This means greater variability in behavior is immediately possible, even in the presence of such a rule noticed as an ongoing process.

Selection

Processes such as experiential avoidance narrow repertoires in part because they impose unhealthy selection criteria onto behavioral streams. Avoiding difficult thoughts or feelings selects any action that temporarily reduces them, from substance use to thought suppression.

Processes such as values identification or motivational interviewing can be seen as attempts to change the selection criteria for action. Values are descriptions regarding the desired qualities of behavior [31]. Clarifying values serves as a way to select among those behavioral alternatives that foster values and those that do not. Most third wave interventions embrace such processes [29] which alone are known to have positive behavioral impact (e.g., [32]).

Retention

Successful forms of psychotherapy include methods to increase the retention of behavior change through practice. Behaviors that are practiced and are organized into skill sets tend to be remembered and deployed. This is perhaps one reason that behavioral methods often end up being shown to be key to the success of evidence-based therapy packages [33]. Homework use consistently correlates with psychotherapy outcomes, as would be expected from this perspective. The central focus on practice seen in mindfulness-based methods is also understandable from this point of view.

Multi-level Selection

Just as cancer can be seen as a problem of the selfishness of cells that can undermine success at the level of the group (the whole organism) so too is the domination of small sets of

behavior (urges to use substances; ruminative thoughts; obsessions; compulsions) over the whole repertoire of a person. Psychotherapy explores the implications of multi-level selection when it promotes success at the level of the whole, and restrains excessive time and attention being given to sub-repertoires at the cost of the whole. This same sensitivity is seen in organizational, family, or couples interventions. For example, in Integrated Behavioral Couple Therapy [34] acceptance of the other person is used to foster attention toward the achievement of communication and intimacy goals of the couple. The concern over fostering social support is in part a recognizing of the highly social nature of human beings.

Multi-Dimensionality

As an empirical fact we know that psychotherapy, contemplative practice, and similar interventions alter the epigenetic regulation of stress related genes (e.g. [35,36]), which suggest that evidence-based psychotherapy may eventually come to be defined in part by its multi-dimensional impact. You can also detect the arrival of multi-dimensional thinking in the increased attention being given in psychotherapy to issues of diet, exercise, sleep, recreation, relaxation, social support, positive psychological growth, and other processes of importance to the health of the whole organism. The recent attempt to redefine clinical psychology as a health services profession can also be seen in this light.

Context

Evolution is always context bound, but when evolutionary principles are used on purpose it is important that the current context support behavior change. Individuals can be empowered to make contact with the current internal and external context by training in greater attentional flexibility, contact with the now, openness, and conscious awareness. All of these processes have been central to third wave behavior therapy interventions [29].

Summary

Problems in psychological functioning can be thought of as narrow or rigid repertoires of behavior, linked to inappropriate selection criteria, at the wrong level or dimension, with insufficient retention of successful variants that may occur given the current context.

Psychotherapy seeks to reverse these processes. In modern contextual forms of evidence-based interventions variation in responding is accomplished by such methods as promoting willingness to experience unwanted private events, exposure to such events, and the use of mindfulness methods to undermine rule-governed insensitivity to direct experience, while present moment awareness promotes greater contingency shaped learning. Healthier selection criteria are established through values clarification and goal setting and successful responses are retained through practice. Greater context sensitivity is promoted through increased mindful awareness, and flexible attention to the now. Multi-level selection is promoted by undermining selfishness and focusing on the good of the whole, and multi-dimensional thinking is promoted by making sure that behavioral targets accommodate what we know about the importance of a balanced and healthy life-style.

Research on psychotherapy interventions may gain precision and scope by targeting the degree to which these interventions promote variation, selection, retention, and context sensitivity. Additionally, the use of evolutionarily sensible dependent variables such as epigenetic markers may help us better examine the impact of psychotherapeutic interventions across evolutionary dimensions. Thus, both conceptually and empirically, psychotherapy can be viewed as a form of applied evolution science.

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